

EARTH SCIENCES

ANISOTROPY'S ROLE IN INTEGRATION OF AMPLITUDE VERSUS OFFSET ANALYSIS (AVO) IN COMPLEX GEOLOGICAL STRUCTURES

Shakarov H.,

*Associate Professor of the department of Geophysics,
Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University,
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Nasibov A.

*PhD candidate of the department of Geophysics,
Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University,
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Abstract

Seismic exploration plays a crucial role in the petroleum industry and is mainly used to detect and map underground geological structure. However, in complex and heterogenous structured geological structures that have multifaceted and intricate characteristics, traditional seismic methods often face significant challenges, resulting in suboptimal data quality and increased operational costs. One of the cost-effective and crucial techniques used in seismic data interpretation is the Amplitude Versus Offset (AVO) analysis. The paper advocates how anisotropy has an impact on AVO response.

Keywords: anisotropy, AVO, Zoeppritz equations, Thomsen's parameters, AVO modeling.

Introduction

Amplitude Versus Offset (AVO) or Amplitude Versus Angle (AVA) method is one of the useful seismic exploration techniques applied to detect hydrocarbon containing reservoir rocks. The main principle of this method is understanding the dependency of seismic amplitude with the distance between the source and receiver. Since complex geological formations have lithological variation, fluid content heterogeneity and irregular geometry, AVO analysis provides a deeper understanding of the subsurface properties and help us to overcome these types of challenges posed by complex geological structures.

The first applications of AVO analysis started within the introduction of reflection coefficients at seismic interfaces. The concept of this technique began to emerge in late 1970s as it was noticed that seismic reflection amplitudes varied with the distance between the seismic source and receiver. This observation led to initial development of AVO interpretation as a quantitative tool.

One of the main principles of AVO analysis is understanding a reason behind variation of reflection coefficients. In order to understand why reflection amplitude varies depending on value of incidence angle, analogous example can be discussed. It is obvious that

if a stone is dropped into water vertically (incidence angle = 0), it will sink instantly. However, if we skim it horizontally, the stone will bounce off the water. The amplitude of the bounce is zero when the stone is thrown vertically while the bounce amplitude increases when we decrease incidence angle. Now, if we replace the water with a rubber and repeat the process, totally different behavior will be observed. The bounce amplitude decreases with angle of incidence, totally opposite to the water case. By applying analogous concepts to seismics, it is possible to identify some properties of interface such as compressional and shear velocities, and densities from reflection amplitude variation with angle of incidence.

Methodology

Thomsen's Parameters

AVO modeling approaches are important when dealing with anisotropic complex geological structures. Anisotropic geological formations have varying physical properties depending on the direction which makes them more complex and challenging to analyze because the velocity of seismic waves varies with the direction of propagation. AVO modeling gives very precise results in isotropic medium, however, it may lead to serious errors in anisotropic geological settings (Figure 1). [1]

Figure 1. Example of how seismic amplitude varies in isotropic and anisotropic medium

Commonly used anisotropy parameters proposed by Thomsen include ϵ (epsilon), δ (delta), and γ (gamma) which quantify the orientation and degree of anisotropy. [3]

ϵ (Epsilon) represents the relative variation of P-wave velocity with respect to the direction of wave propagation.

$$\epsilon = \frac{C_{11}-C_{33}}{2C_{33}} \quad (1)$$

γ (Gamma) is a parameter related to the variation of density (ρ) with respect to the direction of wave propagation in a TI medium

$$\gamma = \frac{C_{66}-C_{44}}{2C_{44}} \quad (2)$$

δ (Delta) represents the variation of S-wave velocity (Vs) with respect to the direction of wave propagation

$$\delta = \frac{(C_{13}+C_{44})^2-(C_{33}-C_{44})^2}{2C_{33}(C_{33}-C_{44})} \quad (3)$$

Thomsen's parameters are very important when dealing with anisotropic geological structures as it

characterizes the anisotropic behavior of rocks which plays crucial role in seismic modeling.

AVO Theory

Different mathematical equations, such as Zoeppritz equations, Aki and Richard approximations, Shuey approximations (1) and other modeling techniques were developed by researchers which describe the relationship between reflection amplitudes and offset, making it possible to interpret these variations.

Zoeppritz equations give more precise results for an interface separated by two isotropic mediums. For that reason, Shuey developed Zoeppritz equation taking Thomsen's parameters into consideration (4).[2]

$$R(\theta) = \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta\alpha}{\alpha} + \frac{\Delta\rho}{\rho} \right) \right] + \left[\frac{1}{2} \frac{\Delta\alpha}{\alpha} - 4 \frac{\beta^2 \Delta\beta}{\alpha^2 \beta} - 2 \frac{\beta^2 \Delta\rho}{\alpha^2 \rho} + \frac{1}{2} \Delta\delta \right] \sin^2 \theta + \left[\frac{1}{2} \frac{\Delta\alpha}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{2} \Delta\epsilon \right] (\tan^2 \theta - \sin^2 \theta) \quad (4)$$

Figure 2. AVO plot for both isotropic and anisotropic case of wells

Case Study

In order to indicate how anisotropy affects Reflection Coefficient, AVO modeling was applied for both isotropic and anisotropic wells. In isotropic medium,

value of the ϵ (Epsilon) and δ (Delta) parameters equal to 0, while the values of these Thomsen’s parameters are given in table 1.

Table 1.

WELL	ϵ (Epsilon)	δ (Delta)
N ₁	1.36	0.7
N ₂	1.81	1.44
N ₃	0.3	-0.42
N ₄	0.64	0.2
N ₅	-0.87	-1.31
N ₆	-0.59	-1.1
N ₇	1.77	1.35

The change of reflection coefficient versus incidence angle was plotted in Figure 2 for both isotropic and anisotropic medium in all 7 wells. This figure shows that Reflection Coefficient of all wells are same when the incidence angle is 0. The main reason of this

is neglect of the second and third parts of the Shuey approximation (5).

When incidence angle increases, Reflection Coefficient start to decrease slowly in isotropic case and rapidly in anisotropic case.

Conclusions

1. The difference between Reflection Coefficient in anisotropic and isotropic medium starts to appear between incidence angle of 2° and 5° .
2. The effect of anisotropic medium on reflection amplitudes is most significant at large incidence angles.

References

1. Jon Downtown, Brian Russell (2000). AVO for managers: pitfalls and solutions. CREWES Research Report 6 Volume 12

2. Shuey, R. T. (1985). A simplification of the Zoeppritz equations. *Geophysics*, 50(4), 609-614.
3. Thomsen L 1986 Weak elastic anisotropy *Geophysics* 51 pp. 1954-1966
4. Thomsen L 2002 Understanding Seismic Anisotropy in Exploration and Exploitation Society of Exploration Geophysicists and European Association of Geoscientists & Engineers Tulsa